

ON THE QUESTION OF STONE–WELES DEFECTS IN GRAPHENE

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In this article, we examined the SW defect in graphene and, after a brief review of previous studies, proposed a model for its origin. This model is based on the thickness of the surface layer $R(I)$ of graphene, equal to the length of the nanocrack L_{nm} . Based on this model, elastic parameters for graphite and graphene are calculated. It is shown that large internal stresses between the graphene plane and the air gap lead to warping of the graphene surface, detected experimentally and theoretically. These internal stresses arise due to the relaxation of the graphene surface. For the same reason, SW defects and other defects arise in graphene through the Frank-Read model. We considered the SW defect from the standpoint of: birth $\rightarrow$ migration $\rightarrow$ annihilation $\rightarrow$ destruction of a graphene sheet. We have already considered the birth of the SW defect. This dislocation (nanocrack) has an autowave character. The maximum speed of movement (migration) of a dislocation (nanocrack) for graphene is $V_{max} \approx 10^4$ m/s. The brake on the movement of dislocations in pure graphene can be the Peierls–Nabarro barrier and internal friction. The Peierls–Nabarro barrier is significantly less than the energy of motion of the dislocation $F(I)_{aP-N} L \ll m V_{max}^2/2$. The brake on the movement of SW dislocations is terahertz oscillations or plasmons in graphene. Annihilation of edge dislocations of opposite signs occurs with the dipole arm in the range $l > 11.5 - 16 \text{ \AA}$. We have presented all the parameters of graphene for calculating the force, deformation and energy criteria for destruction.

Keywords: graphene, defect, surface layer, nanocrack, dislocation, birth, migration, annihilation, destruction of a graphene sheet.

Introduction

In quasi -alarm solids there are topological defects that arise as a result of regrouping of intermediary ties [1]. In Grafen [2] - a crystal with a hexagonal grate - a simple defect of this type is a defect of Stone -Wels (SW) [3]. It is formed when one of the bonds of C-C in the plane of the monofry at an angle of 90° (transformation of Stone -Wels [1]), which leads to the appearance of two seven -angles and two pentagons.

In addition to graphene, graphan [4], graphin [5], graphdin [6], diaman on the SiC (0001), fluorine diaman (F-diaman) on the CuNI substrate (111) [8], as well as quasi-alarmes were synthesized. Composite of polyanilin and oxide graphene [9]. Theoretically proposed a number of stable two-dimensional allotles of

carbon: metal R-10 graphene [10]; carbon monoxide 123-E8Y24-1 [11], two sp^2+sp^3 hybridized structures [12]; PHH-graphite [13]. Most recently, theoretically predicted thermodynamically stable single -layer structures - azuratial [14] and Stone - Wales graphene (SWG) [15]. Stone - Wales graphene, in his two-layer modification, was considered in the work [16].

In this article, we will consider SW - defect in graphene, after a brief review of previous studies, from the standpoint of the causes of its origin.

Structure and properties SW - defect

In [17], two types of SW defects are proposed, namely S-W1 and S-W2, which are caused by a rotation of 90° C-C connections in different directions, as shown in Fig. 1.

Figure 1. Two types of defects of Stone-Wales: (a) Blue connection CC rotates 90° to the defect S-W1; (b) the red bond CC is rotated 90° to the defect of the S-W2 [17].

At the stress of deformation for the graphene sheet $\epsilon = 0.0125$, the energy barrier for the S-W1 defect is 53.9 eV, which is slightly lower than for the S-W2 61.1 eV defect (Fig. 2). In Fig. 3a shows a change in energy

barriers. For the formation of defects S-W1 and S-W2 with an increase in mechanical deformation. Regardless of the level of deformation, the barrier for the S-W1 defect is constantly lower than for S-W2,

Figure 2. The minimum energy path (MEP) of the emergence of the defect S-W1 (A) and the origin of the defect S-W2 (b) during stretching deformation $\varepsilon = 0.0125$ [17].

This indicates that the S-W1 defect is kinetically more profitable than the S-W2. Obviously, the required energy decreases with an increase in deformation. Energy barriers for generating S-W1 and S-W2 are 16.8 eV and 28.9 eV, respectively. In Fig. 3b shows that the strength of the break is reduced with an increase in temperature. The loss of strength of the S-W2 defect is

greater than the S-W1 defect due to its lower energy barrier. In a recent review article [18], it is believed that using the DFT methods, the energy barrier is about 10 eV (compared with work [17]). About the defect of Stone-Weyl (SW), see Fig. 4.

Figure 3. Energy barriers S-W1 (squares) and S-W2 (triangles) depending on the deformation of stretching; The strength for the destruction of the original graphene (green), the defective graphene S-W1 (blue) and defective graphene S-W2 (red) depending on the temperature [17].

Rapid cooling from high temperatures or irradiation with an electron beam can cause SW defects. These results are obtained within the framework of the theory of density functionality using the method of nonequilibrium green functions and in the approximation of local density with various configurations of single-wall graphene nanotubes with SW defects. In this work, the evolution of the passage spectrum with an increase in displacement voltage, states density, voltampere characteristics and the differential conductivity of the puppies

under consideration are calculated. Features of the density of electronic states of defective carbon nanotubes were found with energies of ~ 0.5 eV and -1.92 eV above the level of Fermi. It is shown that the nature of the current flowing through defective graphene nanotubes depends on the length of the defects of the SW. It was revealed that the graphene nanotubes with two sequentially connected SW defects with a displacement voltage of ± 2.6 V has a negative differential conductivity -170 μ S.

Figure 4. Stone-Wales defect: (a) experimental TEM image; (b) DFT calculated image; (c) energy barrier for bond rotation calculated by DFT; (d) Image of sine and cosine-like configurations calculated by DFT [18].

Molecular dynamics (MD) simulations showed that SW defects significantly reduced the strain failure and intrinsic strength of monolayer graphene sheet. SW defects in graphene can alter its physical properties and alter its chemical properties by acting as active sites for the adsorption of other atoms and molecules, increasing local chemical reactivity. In [19], the formation and

movement of SW dislocations in graphene was studied in real time using high-resolution transmission electron microscopy (Fig. 5). SW dislocations move by sliding or crawling at a speed of ~ 0.1 nm/min. Each dislocation creates a deformation field in its vicinity, which extends over a length of ~ 1 nm.

Figure 5. (A) Stone-Wales defect in graphene. (B) Dislocations in graphene. Thin arrows are Burgers vectors. Thick arrows show the directions of displacement of atoms when a dislocation glides to the right. (C) Atomic configuration resulting from sliding. If an electron beam knocks out two labeled atoms, then the dislocation creeps down. (D) Atomic configuration after crawling [19].

Our model of SW – defect (dislocation)

As stated above, SW - defect is formed during rapid cooling from high temperatures or during irradiation with an electron beam. This is not entirely true. In the 20s of the twentieth century, academician A.F. Ioffe conducted a series of experiments with a NaCl crystal and he obtained a fracture of this salt in the amount of 0.4 g/mm² instead of 200 g/mm² according to the quantum mechanical theory of Max Born [20]. A.F. Ioffe related this to the existence of microcracks in the surface layer. Then he dipped a NaCl crystal into water and measured the hardness of its surface, which increased as the surface layer dissolved, approaching the theoretical value. This experiment was called the “Ioffe effect” [21]. Only in 2018 did it become clear to us how theoretically it is possible to determine the thickness of the surface layer (see below), where defects are mainly formed [22]. Thus, for a NaCl crystal, according to our model, $R(I) = 4.6$ nm (which is typical for nanostructures) and the number of monolayers $n = R(I)/a = 8$ (a is the lattice constant). It is not difficult to wash off 8

monolayers of NaCl with water to obtain the Ioffe effect.

Griffiths [23] in the same 20s of the twentieth century examined the change in the energy of a body with a crack under loading and obtained an energy criterion for destruction, according to which a crack acquires the ability to propagate only when the rate of release of elastic energy during growth becomes equal to or exceeds the energy of the newly formed surfaces.

Frenkel [24] and Schottky [25] proposed their models of defects in solids (Fig. 6). A Frenkel defect is formed when an atom (ion) moves from a crystal lattice site to an interstitial site. A Schottky defect is formed when individual atoms located near the surface, as a result of thermal motion, leave the bulk to the surface, and the resulting vacancy then migrates deep into the crystal [26]. These models laid the foundation for the physics of real crystals.

The fact that defects are formed first in the surface layer (Ioffe effect) is due to the fact that atoms (ions)

on the surface have a different environment than the atoms inside the crystal. The possibility of the appearance of surface states was first predicted by Tamm [27]. Such surface states subsequently became known as Tamm states.

Currently, there are two approaches: the Gibbs approach [28], in which the surface layer is conventionally considered as a geometric surface without thickness; the approach of Van der Wals [29], Guggenheim

[30], Rusanov [31], in which the surface layer is considered as a layer of finite thickness. According to modern concepts [32], the surface phase is understood as an ultrathin film (surface layer) that is in equilibrium with a crystalline base (substrate), the properties and structure of which are different from the bulk properties. However, the question of the theoretical “thickness” of this surface layer for various substances remained open until 2018.

Figure 6. Defects according to Frenkel and Schottky [26].

Only after our work [22, 33] did it become clear how the thickness of the surface layer of a solid, which plays a big role in nanotechnology and mesomechanics, can be theoretically determined [34]. We will consider the thickness of the surface layer of graphite and graphene. The works [22, 33] generalize our proposed

$$T_m(r) = T_m(\infty) \cdot (1 - R(I)/r), \quad r \gg R(I),$$

$$T_m(r) = T_m(\infty) \cdot (1 - R(I)/(R(I) + r)), \quad R(0) \leq r \leq R(I). \tag{1}$$

Here the first formula coincides with the formula of R. Tolman [35], where $R(I) = 2\delta$, δ is the Tolman parameter, which is not determined experimentally. The second formula is further defined in the region $R(0) \leq r \leq R(I)$, so that at $r = 0$ the first formula does not go to infinity. The parameter $R(I)$ is related to the surface energy γ by the formula [22]:

$$R(I) = 2\gamma v / RT. \tag{2}$$

Here γ is the surface energy of the massive sample; v – volume of one mole; R – gas constant; T – temperature. In [36] it is shown that, with an accuracy of up to 3%,:

$$\gamma = 0,70 \cdot 10^{-3} \cdot T_m \text{ [J/m}^2\text{]}, \tag{3}$$

where T_m is the melting temperature of the solid (K). The relationship holds for all metals and for other crystalline compounds. At $T = T_m$ from (2) we obtain:

model of the surface layer of atomically smooth metals. To determine the thickness of the surface layer of various compounds, the size dependence of the melting temperature $T_m(r)$ was used:

$$R(I) = L_{nm} = 0,17 \cdot 10^{-9} \cdot \alpha \cdot v \text{ (m)}. \tag{4}$$

Here we took into account that, according to our work [37], the thickness of the surface layer is equal to the length of the nanocrack, i.e. $R(I) = L_{nm}$, and $\alpha = 1 \text{ m}^{-2}$, so that the dimensionality of the quantities is respected.

This model is shown schematically in Fig. 7a. Equation (4) shows that the thickness of the surface layer $R(I)$ and the length of nanocracks L_{nm} are determined by one parameter - the molar (atomic) volume of the element ($v = M/\rho$, M is the molar mass (kg/mol), ρ is the density (kg /m³)), which periodically changes in accordance with table D.I. Mendeleev (Fig. 7b). From Fig. 7b shows that carbon is at the beginning of the periodic table next to boron and beryllium. Using equations (1) – (4) we calculate the surface layer $R(I)$ for graphite and graphene.

Table 1.

Parameters of graphite and grapheme

Carbon	ρ , g/sm ³	T_m , K	$R(I)_a=L_{nma}$, nm	$R(I)_c=L_{nmc}$, nm	γ_a , mJ/m ²	γ_c , mJ/m ²
Graphite	2,26	3970	0,90 (3)	2,46 (3)	2779	591
Graphene	2,26	4510	0,246 (1)	-	3157	-

Figure 7. Schematic representation of the surface layer (a), periodic change atomic volume of elements (b).

Graphite [38] is a thermodynamically stable allotropic modification of carbon - an element of the 4th group of the main subgroup of the 2nd period of the periodic system, serial number 6, atomic mass of a natural mixture of isotopes 12.0107 g/mol. The theoretical density of 2.26 g/cm³ is achieved only in natural graphite. The thickness of the surface layer and the length of graphite nanocracks in the longitudinal direction is $R(I)_a = L_{nma} = 0.90$ nm, and in the perpendicular direction $R(I)_c = L_{nmc} = 2.46$ nm, which is a nanostructure according to Gleiter [39]. The number of graphite monolayers is $n = R(I)/a = 3$, which makes it easy to obtain

Figure 8. – Transformation of the crystal surface

Size effects in the $R(I)$ layer are determined by the entire collective of atoms in the system (collective processes). Such “quasi-classical” size effects are observed only in nanoparticles and nanostructures [41]. Experimentally, $R(I)$ can be observed on very pure single crystals in high vacuum with grazing incidence of X-ray radiation, when the angle of incidence is equal to or less than the critical angle of total internal reflection [32]. When the angle of incidence becomes less than the critical one, the refracted wave decays exponentially in the volume at a characteristic depth of the order of several nanometers (for example, for silicon this depth is $R(I) = 3.2$ nm, and for gold $R(I) = 1.2$ nm) [32].

graphene from it, even mechanically [2]. Graphene is a two-dimensional allotropic modification of carbon, formed by a layer of carbon atoms one atom thick ($R(I) = a = 0.246$ nm - lattice constant), which are in a state of sp^2 hybridization [2]. Carbon atoms in graphene layers are in a three-coordinated state, i.e. each of them forms covalent bonds with three neighbors. As a result, a network of hexagons is formed, the vertices of which are carbon atoms, carbon-carbon bonds form the corresponding sides. The melting point of graphene is $T_m = 4510$ K [40]. In the surface layer $R(I)$, relaxation or reconstruction [32] of atomic monolayers occurs (Fig. 8).

To separate the $R(I)$ layer from the rest of the crystal, it is necessary to expend energy, which is called adhesion energy [42]:

$$W_a = \gamma_1 + \gamma_2 - \gamma_{12} \approx \gamma_1 + \gamma_2 = 1.3\gamma_2, \quad (5)$$

where γ_{12} is the surface energy at the phase interface, which is negligible due to a second-order phase transition.

Internal voltages σ_{is} between phases γ_1 and γ_2 can be calculated using the formula [42]:

$$\sigma_{is} = \sqrt{W_a \cdot \dot{A}}/R(I), \quad (6)$$

where E is Young's modulus of elasticity.

Using equations (5) – (6), we calculate the elastic parameters for graphite and graphene.

Table 2.

Elastic parameters of graphite and grapheme

Carbon	W_{aa} , J/m ²	W_{ac} , J/m ²	σ_{isa} , GPa	σ_{isc} , GPa	E_a , GPa	E_c , GPa
Graphite	3,613	1,323	5,74	1,37	7,59	3,48
Graphene	4,100	-	130,4	-	1020	-

Large internal stresses σ_{is} between the graphene plane and the air gap lead to warping of the graphene surface, which was discovered experimentally and theoretically in [43, 44]. According to the authors of [17, 19, 45], a SW defect can be considered as a dislocation dipole (DD), in which two edge dislocations with opposite signs (see Fig. 1) of the Burgers vector are shifted by one lattice period. As a rule, the presence of DD leads to warping of graphene [43, 44].

For SW dislocations to move in graphene, they need to overcome a potential barrier. Today, there are several mechanisms of dislocation braking, which can be divided into two groups. The first group discusses the inhibition of dislocations due to the presence of potential barriers in crystals caused by various structural defects, including the Peierls–Nabarro barrier. The second group discusses the inhibition of dislocations due to the presence of dynamic interaction in crystals. This includes interaction with electrons, phonons, excitons, magnons and other elementary excitations of the crystal lattice. The role of the latter excitations is insignificant for most crystals, but the interaction with phonons is

most significant. The Peierls–Nabarro barrier always exists, since it is equal to the force of interatomic interaction in solids [46, 47]. In contrast to the Frenkel–Kontorova model [48], as well as works [49, 50] and others, we will propose a model that can be used to estimate the barrier $F(I)_{P-N}$ and $\sigma(I)_{P-N}$ Peierls – Nabarro stress [51]:

$$F(I)_{P-N} = \gamma \cdot R(I) / n = \gamma \cdot a, \quad (7)$$

$$\sigma(I)_{P-N} = F(I)_{P-N} / S = \gamma / a = E \cdot \varepsilon(I),$$

where n is the number of layers in layer $R(I)$; a is the lattice constant; S – barrier area (a^2), $\sigma(I)_{P-N}$, – Peierls–Nabarro stress; E – Young’s modulus; ε represents the relative elongation of the lattice parameter in the direction of the external force F .

Relation (7) shows that the Peierls–Nabarro barrier in the $R(I)$ layer is completely determined by experimentally determined values and is presented in Table. 3. You can add the term $\sin(2\pi z/a)$ to equation (7) and show the relief of the Peierls–Nabarro barrier [49–50] (see Fig. 4d).

Table 3.

Barrier $F(I)$ and $\sigma(I)$ Peierls – Nabarro stress of graphite and grapheme

Carbon	Structure	$F(I)_{aP-N}$, 10 ⁻⁹ N	$F(I)_{cP-N}$, 10 ⁻⁹ N	$\sigma(I)_{aP-N}$, MPa	$\sigma(I)_{cP-N}$, MPa
Graphite	P6 ₃ /mmc	0,23	0,13	3783	294
Graphene	hexagon.	0,26	-	4268	-

From the table Figure 3 shows that the barrier value $F(I)$ and the Peierls–Nabarro stress $\sigma(I)$ for graphite and graphene in the longitudinal plane do not differ much, since the thickness of the surface layer is three graphene monolayers. It follows from this that the SW defect is an edge dislocation in graphene that is capable of moving (Fig. 5). More precisely, a SW defect can be considered as a dislocation dipole (DD), in which two edge dislocations with opposite signs (see Fig. 1) of the Burgers vector are shifted by one lattice period [45]. The second conclusion that follows from table. 2 and 3, is that the SW defect does not arise during the rapid cooling of graphene or when it is irradiated with electrons, but due to the formation of a surface and the appearance of internal stresses in it. The length of the edge dislocation (nanocrack) of graphene is $L_{nma} = 0.246$ nm [52], which after its relaxation becomes equal to $L_{\mu ma} = 24.6$ nm [53]. Let’s look at the table. 2 and consider the question: can internal stresses σ_{is} in the $R(I)$ layer become sources of dislocations? Let us consider the Frank-Reed model for graphene, set out in [54]. According to this model, a dislocation behaves like an elastic thread and bends due to internal stresses $\tau =$

Gb/L , where G is the shear modulus; b – Burgers vector; L – dislocation length. For graphene $G = E/1+\nu = 1457$ GPa [44], $b = 0.24$ nm [45], $L_{nma} = 0.246$ nm [53]. As a result, $\tau = 1421$ GPa instead of $\sigma_{is} = 130.4$ GPa from Table. 2, i.e. $\tau > \sigma_{is}$ and this means that the Frank-Reed model can be a source of dislocations for graphene. The dislocation density is $\rho_{nm} = (L_{nma} b)^{-1}$ [55] and for graphene $\rho_{nm} = 4.2 \cdot 10^{14}$ cm⁻². At such a dislocation density, it turns into a nanocrack [19, 56, 57].

Let us now consider the speed of movement of the nanocrack. The maximum crack propagation speed according to Griffiths theory is [58]:

$$V_C = \beta \cdot V_0 \cdot (1 - \gamma_1 / W_a)^{1/2} \quad (8)$$

and is about 1/3 of the speed of sound V_0 in the material.

After Griffiths, a significant number of works were published in which various models of crack development were analyzed, but we make a choice in work [59], where it became possible to calculate the maximum crack propagation speed V_{max} in solid materials for which the main mechanical characteristics are known (E – Young’s modulus, ν – Poisson’s ratio, ρ – material density):

$$V_{\max} = \frac{dL}{dt} = \sqrt{\frac{1-\nu}{4(1+\nu)[\nu^2 - 3\nu/2 + 7/8] \ln 5,2 - 3\nu/8 + 3/32}} \cdot \sqrt{\frac{E}{\rho}},$$

$$\text{at } \nu = 0,25 \quad V_{\max} = 0,38 \cdot \sqrt{\frac{E}{\rho}}. \quad (9)$$

Using the values from table. 1 and 2, we calculate $V_{\max}$ for graphene: $V_{\max} \approx 10^4$ m/s. The calculated speed of sound in graphene was 50334 m/s, which is much higher than the experimental values for graphite (1470 m/s), diamond (12000 - 18350 m/s), single-walled carbon nanotubes (31470 m/s) and graphene (13600 - 21300 m/s) [60-63]. The average value of 1/3 of the speed of sound in graphene is $1.2 \cdot 10^4$ m/s (from experiment), which almost coincides with the $V_{\max}$ value we calculated using formula (9). This means that the Griffiths formula for the maximum speed of crack propagation is also valid. However, calculating this speed using formula (8) is much more difficult (β , γ_1 , W_a) than using formula (9) - (E , ρ).

Let us summarize the above and imagine the SW defect from the standpoint of: birth $\rightarrow$ migration $\rightarrow$ annihilation $\rightarrow$ destruction of a graphene sheet.

Birth (creation) of SW – dislocations (nanocracks) in graphene

SW – dislocation in graphene occurs due to the formation of a surface and the appearance of internal stresses in it. The length of the edge dislocation (nanocrack) of graphene is $L_{\text{nma}} = 0.246$ nm [52], which after

its relaxation becomes equal to $L_{\text{uma}} = 24.6$ nm [53]. It was shown above that the Frank-Reed model can be a source of dislocations for graphene. The birth of a dislocation dipole in graphene is taken from [57] and shown in Fig. 9, however, the interpretation of the results in this work is different from that proposed by us. This dislocation (nanocrack) has an autowave character, shown in Fig. 4d and here's why? In open systems of inanimate nature, which constantly receive negative entropy and matter from the external environment, stationary nonequilibrium states with a high degree of order can arise [64, 65]. The processes in which self-organization phenomena occur include autowave processes (AWP) [66-70]. AWP is usually understood as a self-sustaining wave process (including stationary structures) in an active nonlinear medium, which maintains its characteristics constant due to an energy source distributed in the medium [71-73].

These characteristics - period, wavelength (or pulse), propagation speed, amplitude and shape - in a steady state depend only on the local properties of the medium and do not depend on the initial ones, but rather far from the boundaries of the medium and from the boundary conditions.

Figure 9. Birth of a dislocation dipole in graphene. The top panels show the original AC-HRTEM images with low-pass Fourier filtering applied, while the bottom panels show frames with maximum filtering applied for better visibility. In panel a, two atoms have been removed, forming a divacancy. In each subsequent panel b–e, two more atoms were removed and the defect underwent significant reorganization. In panel e, after ten missing atoms, the defect structure has reorganized into a dislocation dipole with two edge dislocations at its ends pointing away from each other. The scale bar is 1 nm [57].

Migration of SW – dislocations (nanocracks) in graphene

We showed above that the maximum speed of movement (migration) of a dislocation (nanocrack) for graphene is $V_{\max} \approx 10^4$ m/s. The brake on the movement of dislocations in pure graphene can be the Peierls–Nabarro barrier and internal friction. The Peierls–Nabarro barrier is significantly less than the energy of motion of the dislocation $F(I)_{\text{aP-N}} L \ll m V_{\max}^2/2$.

A measure of internal friction is the inverse quality factor Q^{-1} , which is equal according to Debye [74]:

$$Q^{-1} = 2Q_{\max}^{-1} \frac{2\pi f\tau}{1 + (2\pi f\tau)^2}, \quad (10)$$

where f is the vibration frequency of the sample, τ is the relaxation time.

The maximum value of internal friction is achieved at $2\pi f\tau = 1$. The relaxation time τ can be determined for the layer R(I), knowing the speed of sound in graphene - $\tau_1 = R(I)/v$: $\tau = 0.246 \cdot 10^{-9}/13600 = 1.8 \cdot 10^{-14}$ s, $f = 0.3 \cdot 10^{14} = 30 \cdot 10^{12}$ Hz = 30 THz. This means that a terahertz oscillation (radiation) is observed for the R(I) layer in graphene (Fig. 10) [75]. In graphene,

the maximum frequency f of low-amplitude phonon vibrations is 46 THz [76, 77], which is in good agreement

with our value. This means that the brake on the movement of SW dislocations is terahertz vibrations or plasmons in graphene.

Figure 10. Spectrum of electromagnetic waves and terahertz "dip".

In recent years, a number of both theoretical [78–80] and experimental [81–83] works have appeared devoted to the study of plasmons in graphene. The use of graphene plasmons makes it possible to obtain significantly stronger nonlinear effects in the THz frequency range compared to THz photons. This occurs due to the fact that the group velocity of plasmons in graphene is two to three orders of magnitude lower than the speed of light in vacuum and the plasmon field is highly localized near the graphene layer. This, in turn, leads to significant inhibition of the movement of dislocations.

Annihilation of SW – dislocations (nanocracks) in graphene

The dynamics of SW dislocations and their annihilation were carried out in a number of works [84–86]. These works described the annihilation of a pair of dislocations using a combined DFT and MD method. We

will take the most recent work on the motion of dislocations and their annihilation [45, 87–89]. In [87], the time evolution of a pair of dislocations in graphene is studied by performing molecular dynamics simulations on a subnanosecond scale based on the tight coupling density functional method. The simulation shows self-healing of the graphene lattice, leading to complete annihilation of dislocations, that is, to the formation of the pristine graphene structure. Unusual local bond states arise mainly due to the geometric features of the out-of-plane deformation of dislocation structures. Dislocation annihilation was studied by DFTB/MD simulation of graphene containing dislocations on a subnanosecond scale. To approximate the local heating caused by electron beam irradiation and induce structural changes within the available simulation time, the system temperature was between 3000 and 3500 K. In Fig. 11 compares DFTB results with DFT results for paired dislocation structures.

Figure 11. Comparison of DFTB results (left) with DFT results (right) [87].

It was shown in [88] that an arm length of $9.3 \text{ \AA}$ is close to the equilibrium value at which dislocation annihilation is not observed, and annihilation occurs at an arm length $l > 11.5 \text{ \AA}$. It was established in [89] that annihilation is possible for dislocation dipoles with arm length $l > 16 \text{ \AA}$. Annihilation can easily occur at high temperatures.

Let us turn to the data obtained within the framework of our model. The increase in dislocation density during deformation is caused by the intersection of newly generated and existing dislocations. The average

path length of dislocations L with the Burgers vector b and their density ρ depend on the degree of deformation ε as [90]:

$$\varepsilon_{nm} = \rho_{nm} \cdot b \cdot L_{nm} \quad (11)$$

For graphene $\rho_{nm} = 4.2 \cdot 10^{18} \text{ m}^{-2}$, $b = 0.24 \cdot 10^{-9} \text{ m}$, $L_{nma} = 0.246 \cdot 10^{-9} \text{ m}$, then it turns out that $\varepsilon_{nm} = 0.248$. In [45], at $T = 300 \text{ K}$ for dislocations in graphene with a dipole arm $l = 15 \text{ \AA}$, the value $\varepsilon_F = 0.24$ was obtained. This result was obtained by the MD method and differs slightly from our value of ε_{nm} . The internal stresses can be estimated in the form [90]:

$$\sigma = \tilde{N}_1 \cdot G \cdot b \cdot \rho^{1/2}, \quad (12)$$

where C_1 is a constant of the order of 0.2 and G is the shear modulus.

For graphene $\rho_{nm} = 4.2 \cdot 10^{18} \text{ m}^{-2}$ $b = 0.24 \cdot 10^{-9} \text{ m}$, $C_1 = 0.2$, $G = 1457 \cdot 10^9 \text{ Pa}$, then it turns out that $\sigma = 139.8 \text{ GPa}$, instead of $\sigma = 130.4 \text{ GPa}$ (Table 2). The given examples show the consistency of our model.

Let us now estimate the dipole arm in our model for graphene. Annihilation of edge dislocations of opposite signs in the same slip plane can occur even at low temperatures, reducing the dislocation density (Fig. 11). The distance between edge dislocations of opposite signs is equal to $l_p = 1/\rho^{1/2}$, where ρ is the dislocation density, which is related to the dislocation shoulder by the expression:

$$l = \alpha \cdot l_p = \alpha / \rho^{1/2} \approx 3 / \rho^{1/2}, \quad (13)$$

where $\alpha = 3$, taken from our work [53], where $\alpha = \gamma_2/\gamma_1 \approx 3$.

For graphene $\rho = 4.2 \cdot 10^{18} \text{ m}^{-2}$ and according to our model $l = 14.6 \text{ \AA}$. Annihilation of edge dislocations of opposite signs occurs according to the data of [88, 89] with a dipole shoulder in the range $l > 11.5 - 16 \text{ \AA}$, which agrees well with our data.

$$L_{nm} \rightarrow L_{\mu m} = 10^2 \cdot L_{nm} \rightarrow L_C = 10^4 \cdot L_{nm} = 0,17 \cdot 10^{-5} \cdot M / \rho. \quad (17)$$

Tables 1-3 show all graphene parameters for calculating force, deformation and energy failure criteria.

Conclusions

The topological Stone–Wales defect we considered is the most important defect in graphene, to which a large number of theoretical and experimental works are devoted and which continue to this day. In this study, we also proposed our own model of a SW defect from the standpoint of: birth $\rightarrow$ migration $\rightarrow$ annihilation $\rightarrow$ destruction of a graphene sheet. In the future, we plan to experimentally test some of the results of the proposed model.

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Fracture of a graphene sheet

For the destruction of a solid body, force, deformation and energy failure criteria have been developed. There is the following connection between them [91]:

$$\frac{K_{1N}^2(1-\mu^2)}{E} = 2\delta_{1N}\sigma_B = G_{1N} = J_{1N} = 2\gamma = W_a, \quad (14)$$

where K_{Ic} is the critical stress intensity factor, the force criterion for destruction; E - elastic modulus; μ - Poisson's ratio; δ_{Ic} - critical opening at the crack tip, deformation criterion of destruction; σ_B - tensile strength; G_{Ic} - critical intensity of released energy, energy criterion of destruction; J_{Ic} - critical j-integral, energy criterion of destruction; γ - surface energy, W_a - adhesion energy.

Wherein:

$$K_{1N} = \sqrt{EJ_{1N}}. \quad (15)$$

In the case of a plate with a crack L_C :

$$\hat{E}_{1N} = \sigma_{is} \sqrt{L_N}, \quad \delta_{1N} = K_{1N}^2 / \sigma_{is} \cdot E. \quad (16)$$

According to our work [51], the length of a nanocrack varies according to the law:

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